

USER NEEDS FOR A TEXT SUITE FOR ADVANCED DIGITAL RESEARCH

dr. Max Kemman

ir. Nick Jelacic

Guido de Moor MSc

Marenne Massop MSc

ir. Tommy van der Vorst

COMMISSIONED BY
KB

PUBLICATION NUMBER
2022.024-2212

DATE
Utrecht, March 31st 2022

Table of Contents

Summary	3
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Context	6
1.2 Goal.....	6
1.3 Research method	6
1.4 Contents of this report	7
2 The concept of a text suite	8
2.1 Challenges of research into user requirements	8
2.2 Knowledge about users	9
2.3 A generic description of the research process	13
3 Positioning a text suite	17
3.1 Users and their needs	17
3.2 Text collections.....	20
3.3 Collaborating with heritage organisations	21
4 Functional requirements	23
4.1 Survey respondents.....	23
4.2 Functionalities	26
4.3 Development of a text suite by the KB	42
5 Conclusions and recommendations	44
5.1 Conclusions	44
5.2 Recommendations.....	46
Appendix 1. Interviewees	47

Summary

The amount of research carried out on digital historical material that the national library of the Netherlands (KB) preserves and makes accessible, is increasing. At the same time, the KB has observed a widening gap between for instance Delpher and DBNL on the one hand and Dataservices on the other. Due to a combination of factors including the emergence of Open Science, users' personal development and the availability of digital heritage collections, the need for more analysis options in multiple external (also outside KB) collections in conjunction with a single interface seems to be growing among both professional and non-professional researchers. However, since users cannot (always) write own code, neither Delpher, DBNL nor Dataservices can fully meet their research needs.

Against this backdrop, the KB plans to explore whether its users want the KB to develop an analysis platform where several KB as well as external collections can be analysed in an integrated way. The (largely) text-based collections that the KB manages, including those already accessible in Delpher and DBNL, serve as a starting point for what the KB calls a "text suite".

This exploration's aim is to develop a **demand-driven description** of a text suite, focussing on user requirements. The study comprises three research tracks that need to be addressed in relation to each other:

1. Identify **users and their requirements**
2. Map **text collections** (also outside KB) eligible for the text suite
3. Involve other **heritage organisations** to find out if they would be interested in a joint text suite.

For this study, interviews were held with KB staff, developers of similar analysis tools (Nederlab, Media Suite, impresso) and potential user groups (including historians, literary scholars, digital humanities, amateur researchers, journalists). The input from these interviews was structured based on the eight functionalities that can be considered for a text suite. Through an online survey with 873 respondents, a broad audience was consulted to determine which options generate the most added value.

Conclusions regarding users and their requirements

DBNL and Delpher user research provides **limited indications of a text suite's added value**. The more advanced functionalities already available are only used to a limited extent. Users also do not mention advanced methods for research, or only to a limited extent, as options for improving these services. Alternative research systems also provide limited indications of a text suite's added value. User research has seldom been carried out and these systems are mainly aimed at humanities scholars. The interviews show that it seems difficult to bridge the gap between Delpher or DBNL and Dataservices, i.e. between on the one hand user-friendly searching or reading and on the other hand advanced analysis through programming. Interviewees appear to be firmly divided on these extremes, and so there is limited need for a middle ground. A text suite furthermore seems to fit (mainly professional) research needs. Amateur researchers and respondents who use Delpher and/or DBNL for pleasure have less need for a new service and mainly see room for improvement in the existing services.

Based on a literature review, we distinguish **four research phases**: discovery, selection, analysis and dissemination. There is **a clear need for advanced options for the discovery phase**. The interviewees and online survey respondents either express an explicit need for visualisations of available collections and search results, or indicate that they would use

these if available. **Advanced options are also clearly needed for the selection phase.** The interviewees and online survey respondents indicate a strong need to compile collections of relevant sources. However, there is **no clear need for advanced capabilities in the analysis phase.** Although this was the starting point for the exploration, interviewees and online survey respondents indicate they have less need for these and may not even use them if offered. There are three main arguments: First, because of the great heterogeneity of source material within the KB and elsewhere, researchers prefer to collate everything on their own computer for analysis. The alternative is that a text suite makes it possible to import sources, which raises questions about the sustainable preservation of composite collections. Second, due to the rapid development of quantitative analysis tools, interviewees foresee a risk with the KB offering tools that soon become outdated, especially if they are not utilised enough to warrant significant continuous development. Finally, we note that where analysis functionality is offered on existing platforms (e.g. the n-gram viewer in DBNL or frequency analysis in Nederlab), this does not seem to lead to recognition and broad application for new research questions. The latent need for such functionalities therefore seems limited. Interviewees do, however, see added value in supporting the further process of analysing sources. This can be achieved by offering some basic functions. Moreover, it could involve providing documentation or an explanation how to analyse (large) text collections. A text suite can also play an educational role here. Finally, there is **no clear need for advanced features in the dissemination phase.** The online survey respondents indicated less need for these. The interviewees expressed a great need to be able to collaborate as a community on text collections, share annotations and improve metadata and OCR. However, this raises issues regarding the sustainable storage and the quality and uniformity of (meta)data.

Conclusions regarding the need for text collections

Expanding collections is consistently mentioned in DBNL and Delpher user research as the most important area for improvement. Furthermore, we find that people need a wide variety of text collections, depending on their personal research questions. These range from regional sources to international data collections, and from data to not yet machine-readable sources. It is **not feasible to make a selection of collections** that every user can work with entirely.

Interviewees furthermore note that combining collections is a major challenge, as providers of varying text collections keep different metadata that is difficult to harmonise. Other research systems also show that combining multiple collections with enrichments is very labour-intensive and/or computationally intensive. The importance of incorporating external collections depends partly on whether a text suite offers functionalities for the analysis phase. If so, it will then be necessary to analyse external sources within a text suite so that a researcher can work within a single environment. If researchers export data from a text suite for analysing on their own computer, this reduces the need for full integration of multiple text collections.

Conclusions regarding collaboration with heritage organisations

Interviewees mainly see cooperation as important for increasing the availability of collections and for involving the necessary (technological) expertise. However, they also indicate that too many partners will make development too sluggish as various interests will have to be coordinated. Particularly when combining several text collections, there is a risk that too much time will be lost in harmonising metadata. **The KB has sufficient material to form a starting point for a text suite with Delpher and DBNL, as well as with other internal collections.** The major next step appears to be the Nationaal Archief (Dutch National Archives) collections.

Recommendations

We conclude there are sufficient opportunities for developing a text suite. For this development, we provide the following recommendations:

1. **Position a text suite as a corpus selection tool and support the discovery and selection research phases.** A text suite hereby functions as a user-friendly front end to Dataservices with more advanced features that do not fit within Delpher and DBNL. Users can then make their own selection of sources and export them (possibly after approval by a KB employee).
2. **Develop advanced search and selection functionalities.** We recommend including the following functionalities:
 - a. search bar
 - b. filtering based on metadata fields
 - c. filtering search results based on metadata fields
 - d. visualisations of available sources
 - e. visualisations of search results
 - f. options for compiling your own collections, e.g. by adding individual sources or large quantities of search results
 - g. searching within your own collections
 - h. filtering within your own collections based on metadata fields
 - i. visualisations of your own collections
 - j. options to export sources and/or collections.
3. **Recalibrate the aims regarding analysis support.** We see insufficient commonly shared needs for developing an advanced analysis tool. Moreover, in terms of analysis methodology, we see insufficient need to bridge the gap between Delpher and DBNL on the one hand and Dataservices on the other. We also see a risk of analysis tools becoming outdated and/or being underused for continuous development, which could harm the KB's image. We find that educational support is needed for the analysis phase. This could include tutorials and documentation on how to use a selection of sources from a text suite sources with other software tools.
4. **Start with a broad base of KB collections and explore collaboration with the Nationaal Archief (Dutch National Archives).** There is too much diversity in the collections with different metadata and quality standards to enable a text suite to start making a large number of text collections from different providers equally searchable. Moreover, the KB manages a very rich diversity of collections which provide a sufficient starting point for a text suite. Nationaal Archief could be an added value partner from the start because then the archival material perspective (as opposed to library collections) could be incorporated in the development. Moreover, Nationaal Archief manages richly diverse collections too and in recent years has been making great strides in having collections available for digital infrastructures.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The amount of research conducted on digital historical material that the national library of the Netherlands (KB) preserves and makes accessible, is increasing. At the same time the KB has noticed a widening gap between for instance Delpher¹ and DBNL² on the one hand and Dataservices³ on the other. Due to a combination of factors including the emergence of Open Science, users' personal development and the availability of digital heritage collections, the need for more analysis capability for multiple external (also outside KB) collections in conjunction with a single interface seems to be growing among both professional and non-professional researchers. However, since users cannot (always) write their own code, neither Delpher, DBNL nor Dataservices can fully meet their research requirements. Aiming to bridge this gap, several initiatives have been and are building more advanced systems or suites, where more complex analyses can be done on the collections these initiatives have obtained through for example Dataservices.

Against this backdrop, the KB plans to explore whether its users need the KB to develop an analysis platform where several KB as well as external collections can be analysed in an integrated way. The (largely) text-based collections the KB manages, including those already accessible in Delpher and DBNL, serve as a starting point for what the KB therefore calls a "text suite". Before starting on a development process, the KB asked Dialogic *Innovation & Interaction* to explore the demand and opportunities for a text suite.

1.2 Goal

The aim of the exploration is to develop a **demand-driven description** of a text suite, with a focus on user requirements. The study comprises three research tracks that need to be addressed in relation to each other:

4. Identify **users and their requirements** (these include professional researchers such as historians, literature scholars, journalists, but also amateur researchers such as genealogists);
5. Map **text collections** (also outside KB) eligible for the text suite;
6. Involve other **heritage organisations** (such as university libraries and partners in the Dutch Digital Heritage Network⁴) to find out if they would be interested in a joint text suite.

1.3 Research method

The exploration was carried out in two phases. First, for the **divergent phase**, user needs and input were collected broadly with no delimitations. Nine exploratory interviews were conducted with KB staff and developers of similar analysis tools (Nederlab, Media Suite, impresso) to gain insight into what a text suite could be. In addition, desk research was carried out on what is already known about user requirements and text suites. Eight group

¹ Delpher is the KB search portal for digitised Dutch newspapers, books and magazines, see [delpher.nl]

² DBNL is the KB's digital collection of Dutch literary works, see [dbnl.org]

³ Dataservices refers to KB's datasets and API endpoints for its digital collections, including Delpher and DBNL, see [kb.nl]

⁴ [netwerkdigitaal erfgoed.nl]

interviews were then held with various potential user groups or cooperation partners to gain more insight in specific needs and options regarding a text suite. For the list of interviewees, see Appendix 1. During the subsequent **convergent phase**, the gathered information was structured into eight different functionalities that can form a text suite. Through an online survey with 873 respondents, a wide audience was consulted to discover which options generate the most added value.

1.4 Contents of this report

In the remainder of this report, we review the results of the various research steps that ultimately led to the demand-driven description of a text suite. In Chapter 2 we explain the outcome of the desk research to arrive at a conceptualisation of a text suite and how it fits in research processes that include textual collections. In Chapter 3 we discuss the findings from the interviews. These include how the various user groups view the concept of a text suite, what text collections they consider important and which collaboration partners they see as relevant. Chapter 4 presents the results of the online survey to quantitatively underpin a text suite's functional requirements. Finally, in Chapter 5 we present our conclusions regarding the three research tracks (user requirements, text collections, heritage organisations) and offer recommendations for developing a text suite.

2 The concept of a text suite

In this chapter we discuss the results of the desk research to determine what a text suite could be. We start by describing the complex challenge of researching user requirements for a text suite in section 2.1. In section 2.2 we discuss what knowledge is available about users within the KB and in other research systems (Nederlab, impresso and the Media Suite). Finally, section 2.3 presents a schematic description of the research process with regard to text collections. The schema is used in this report to position a text suite within the research process.

2.1 Challenges of research into user requirements

The KB is the national library of the Netherlands and, in line with its mission, serves all Dutch citizens. The development of new services must therefore take into account a very diverse public with different questions, expectations and wishes. For example, the 2020 KB Annual Report⁵ shows that 4% of citizens in the Netherlands used Delpher in 2018, visiting it a total of 2.5 million times. In 2019, Delpher was visited as many as 3.3 million times and in the process, a document opened on 38.3 million occasions. This increase in usage continued in 2020, when the service was visited 4.5 million times and the number of times people opened a file was 57.9 million. DBNL was visited 4.2 million times by 9% of Dutch citizens in 2018. In 2019, user numbers grew to 10% of the population with 10.1 million titles accessed, and in 2020, this rose to 11 million. Dataservices was used by 35 research projects and heritage institutions in 2019 and in 2020 this dropped slightly to 32 projects and institutions.

The large scale makes user research challenging. It is not only about many users, but also about many *different* users. Users cannot be seen as an individual group with unambiguous wants and needs, but as a **wide variety** of groups, each with their own habits, expectations and objectives. Another complexity is that research services such as a text suite are not entirely independent, but part of a **broader research process** of collecting, analysing, interpreting and documenting.⁶ Because the requirements for a text suite might depend on the rest of the research process, it is not easy to draw up an unambiguous list of user wants and needs, as this process varies from user to user.⁷ A final complexity is that user needs and wants **change over time**, also in response to what is offered. For example, an implemented functionality may lead to people wanting adjacent functions they were previously unaware of ('latent demand') and users' knowledge level may increase through usage. Both variations in the population are likely to change. During implementation, a certain degree of flexibility is apparently required in order to cope with changing demands.

⁵ 2020 national library annual report, pp. 81-85. [In Dutch]. (It is not known what percentage of the Dutch population used Delpher in 2019).

⁶ Rik Hoekstra & Marijn Koolen (2019). Data scopes for digital history research. *Historical Methods: A Journal of Quantitative and Interdisciplinary History*, 52(2), 79-94.

⁷ Max Kemman & Martijn Kleppe (2015). User Required? On the Value of User Research in the Digital Humanities. In *Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings* (No. 116, pp. 63-74). Linköping University Electronic Press.

2.2 Knowledge about users

2.2.1 Users of Delpher and DBNL

The KB regularly conducts user satisfaction surveys for its Delpher and DBNL services. These surveys provide insight into how users experience these services. In addition, the surveys identify some of these services' limitations and these could also be addressed by means of a text suite.

DBNL user research⁸ shows that visitors' primary areas of interest are Dutch and Flemish literature (78% and 40% respectively), cultural history (63%) and language and linguistics (30%). The standard search functionality and the options to consult and read full text within the web environment are used most often. Users hardly know about other (advanced) functionalities such as the General Literary Lexicon, the Atlas, the Calendarium or the n-gram viewer. Feedback on improvement is mainly regarding improving the search functionality and expanding the collection.

Delpher user research⁹ shows that visitors' primary areas of interest are history (83%) and genealogy (59%). The standard search functionality is used most frequently for this and the extended search functions are also well known. "Hidden" functions are notably only used to a very limited extent. This may indicate that the functions are justifiably not immediately visible, but it is also possible that if functions are not immediately visible and understandable, users are not aware of the options available. For example, more than half of the respondents do not know about functionalities such as adding texts to favourites and using a permanent URL for sharing. Feedback on improvement is mainly related to improving the search functionality, for example through more refined filtering options, and expanding the collection. This collection aspect also stands out in academic discussions on Delpher, including critical analyses of selection procedures for digitisation¹⁰ and the impact of copyright and OCR quality limitations.¹¹

Five personas have also been developed for Delpher, fictional individuals who represent a user group. The personas are a researcher, student, secondary school teacher, interested citizen and novice data researcher. The dimensions that are distinguished include to what extent users are patient or expect immediate results, work purposefully or allow more serendipity, and whether they work independently or expect more support.

To summarise, the user surveys and personas do not provide a direct positioning of a text suite in relation to Delpher and DBNL. Notably, the more advanced options, where available, are only used to a limited extent and there is little demand for more advanced functionality.

2.2.2 Knowledge about users of other research systems

In addition to the existing KB, Delpher and DBNL systems, this study investigated three other systems: Nederlab, impresso and the Media Suite. The question is whether these systems

⁸ MWM² (2019). Bezoekers van DBNL geven hun mening. Klanttevredenheidsonderzoek naar de website dbnl.org.

⁹ MWM² (2020). Bezoekers van Delpher geven hun mening. Klanttevredenheidsonderzoek naar de website Delpher.nl.

¹⁰ Van Krieken, K. (2015). Using Digital Archives in Quantitative Discourse Studies: Methodological Reflections. *Tijdschrift Voor Tijdschriftstudies*, 0(38), 43. [doi:10.18352/ts.343]

¹¹ Smits, T. (2014). *TS Tools: Problems and possibilities of digital newspaper and periodical archives*, 8.

can serve as inspiration, but also what added value a text suite could bring in addition to these existing systems.

Nederlab¹² is a research platform aimed at diachronical research from the year 800 to the present. For this purpose, various collections have been combined within one system, including DBNL, the KB newspaper collection and Early Dutch Books Online (also available in Delpher), Dutch parliamentary proceedings and various collections of letters and diaries.¹³ For the Nederlab grant application,¹⁴ approximately 150 researchers in the humanities were consulted on what kind of diachronic research they would like to conduct. Four types of research were identified: 1) tracing innovations or the beginning of a shift; 2) determining the dissemination of changes; 3) establishing (statistical) links and networks; 4) detecting similarities and differences between texts. In order to accommodate these four categories, the most important metadata proposed that should be provided was insight in time, place,

The screenshot shows the Nederlab search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo and menu items: home, collecties, zoeken, over nederlab, bronnen, help, login. Below this is a search bar with three options: zoeken in tekst (selected), zoeken in titelgegevens, and zoeken in auteursgegevens. The search results show 21,012 documents found for the query 'koninklijke bibliotheek'. The interface includes filters for genre, collection, and text availability. The search results list several items, each with its title, author, genre, and collection information.

alle woorden: "koninklijke" "bibliotheek", gezocht in tekst, metadata van bron: tekst
aanwezig | 21.012 documenten gevonden

beperk samenstelling
 onzelfstandige titels
 zelfstandige titels
 koepeltitels
 herdrukken uitsluiten

beperk tot genre(s)
 reset zoek
 fictie
 non-fictie
 periodieken
 bloemtezing
 hertaling
 verzameld werk
 verzamelhandschrift

beperk tot collectie(s)
 Acta Zuid-Holland
 Beschrijvinge Oostindische Compagnie
 Briefwisseling Heinsius
 Brieven-Corresp. 1900
 Brieven Van Gogh
 CLVN
 CRM
 Corpus-Middelnerlands
 Corpus-Oudnerlands
 Correspondentie Clusius
 DBNL
 Dagboek De Clercq
 Dagboeken Aalberse
 Dagboeken De Beaufort
 EDBO
 Eindhovenencorpus-2.0
 Gekaapte brieven
 Geleerdenbrieven
 KB kranten
 Notulen Staten van Holland
 SoNaR
 Staten-Generaal Digitaal
 Varia

aanwezigheid tekst
 tekst aanwezig ✓
 verrijkingen aanwezig

De natuurlunde van het geheel: Een 13de-eeuws middelnerlands leerdicht
 uitgave: ca. 1275-1300
 auteur: anoniem Natuurlunde van het geheel, De (-)
 genre: fictie, non-fictie, poezie, leerdicht, artesliteratuur, natuurlunde, sterrenkunde
 collectie: DBNL
 aantal hits: 32

Een scone leeringe om salich te sterven
 uitgave: 1500
 auteur: J. van der Heijden (Dordrecht (Zuid-Holland), 1865-Jakarta, 1928) anoniem Scone leeringe om salich te sterven, Een (-)
 genre: fictie, non-fictie, proza, traktaat
 collectie: DBNL
 aantal hits: 17

Album Joannis Rotarii (Johan Radermacher)
 uitgave: ca. 1560-1620
 auteur: Johan Radermacher (de Oude) (Aken (Rijnland), 1538-Middelburg (Zeeland), 1617)
 genre: fictie, non-fictie, proza, poezie, egodocumenten, gedichten/dichtbundel, liederen/lijdes, brieven
 collectie: DBNL
 aantal hits: 21

De Psalmen Davids, ende ander lofsanghen
 uitgave: 1566
 auteur: Petrus Datheen (Kassel (Frans Vlaanderen), ca. 1531-Elbing (Polen), 1588)
 genre: fictie, non-fictie, poezie, liederen/lijdes, bijbel/bijbelteksten
 collectie: DBNL
 aantal hits: 6

Het bosken
 uitgave: ca. 1566
 auteur: Jan van der Noot (Brecht (Antwerpen), ca. 1539-Antwerpen (Antwerpen), ca. 1595) W.A.P. Smit (Heumen (Gelderland), 1903-Utrecht (Utrecht), 1986)
 genre: fictie, poezie, gedichten/dichtbundel, liederen/lijdes
 collectie: DBNL
 aantal hits: 26

Figure 1. Screenshot of Nederlab with the query "koninklijke bibliotheek" (2 September 2021)

¹² [nederlab.nl]

¹³ Overzicht van de in Nederlab opgenomen collecties [nederlab.nl]

¹⁴ Nederlab (2011). Nederlab, een laboratorium voor onderzoek naar de veranderingspatronen in de Nederlandse taal en cultuur. *NWO Investment Subsidy NWO Large 2011-2012 aanvraag*. [nederlab.nl]

author data and text type (fiction, non-fiction, newspapers, ego documents, etc.). A 2015 researcher evaluation shows that Nederlab offers an impressive collection with the potential for an infinite number of questions, but that these questions are **largely limited to qualitative analysis**.¹⁵ However, apparently no comprehensive user evaluation has been conducted.

Impresso¹⁶ is a search engine for Swiss and Luxembourgish newspapers with a focus on **supporting the search process with innovative enhancements** such as named entities (identification of persons, locations, organisations), topic models (clusters of co-occurring words that indicate shared topics), image search, text re-use detection and search query suggestions based on word embeddings. In preparation for its development, the researchers reviewed other digital newspaper systems, including Delpher.¹⁷ They scored Delpher highly

Figure 2. Screenshot of impresso with the query "bibliothèque" (2 September 2021)

¹⁵ Struik, Tara (2015). Nederlab: An evaluation. *researchpaper anglistiek Radboud Universiteit*. [nederlab.nl]

¹⁶ [impresso-project.ch]

¹⁷ Ehrmann, M., Bunout, E., & Düring, M. (2017). Historical Newspaper User Interfaces: A Review. In *WLIC proceedings*. Athens, Greece.

on search options, but slightly lower on sorting, filtering and displaying results. They missed enrichments, APIs and information about digitisation in Delpher. The researchers behind *impresso* have organised various user workshops, but no study has been published with a more comprehensive user evaluation.

The **Media Suite**¹⁸ is a research platform explicitly developed to accommodate the great variety of research questions and methods in the humanities. For this reason, **a hybrid system was chosen with a graphical user interface together with Jupyter Notebooks** wherein a user can code.¹⁹ The system furthermore engages with the concept of *generous interfaces*. As such, the guiding principle is that the interface should stimulate the user and immediately indicate the options. This is in contrast to the standard search bar, where the user has to judge for themselves what is of interest and only after conducting a

The screenshot shows the Media Suite search interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo 'CLARIAH MEDIA SUITE' and links for 'Data', 'Tools', 'About', 'Blog', 'Learn', 'Help', 'Contact', and 'Login'. Below the navigation bar, the search area is titled 'Search' and shows a search for 'koninklijke bibliotheek' in the 'Newspaper Collection' (133.719.514 items). The search results are displayed in a list format, with a sidebar on the left for filtering. The sidebar has three main sections: 'Periode' (Time Period), 'Soort bericht' (Type of report), and 'Verspreidingsgebied' (Distribution area). The 'Periode' section shows filters for 17e eeuw (6819), 18e eeuw (79205), 19e eeuw (1593949), 20e eeuw (12382872), and Empty field (0). The 'Soort bericht' section shows filters for advertentie (4265180), artikel (9231610), Empty field (0), familiebericht (291660), and illustratie met onderschrift (274395). The 'Verspreidingsgebied' section shows filters for Empty field (19499), Landelijk (6082462), Nederlands Indië / Indonesië (65331), and Nederlands-Indië / Indonesië (1253598). The search results list includes three items, each with a checkbox, a title, a subtitle, and a snippet of text. The first item is 'De nieuwe Koninklijke Bibliotheek te Berlijn.' with a subtitle 'Krantentitel: Haagsche courant' and a snippet of text. The second item is 'OFFICIEELE BERICHTEN uit de Staatscourant.' with a subtitle 'Krantentitel: Haagsche courant' and a snippet of text. The third item is 'KONINKLIJKE BIBLIOTHEEK GESLOTEN.' with a subtitle 'Krantentitel: Amigoe di Curacao : weekblad voor de Curacaosche eilanden' and a snippet of text. The search results are displayed in a list format with a pagination bar at the top of the results area showing '1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 NEXT LAST'.

Figure 3. Screenshot of Media Suite with the query "koninklijke bibliotheek" (2 September 2021)

¹⁸ [mediasuite.clariah.nl]

¹⁹ Melgar-Estrada, L., et al. (2019, March). The CLARIAH Media Suite: A Hybrid Approach to System Design in the Humanities. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Human Information Interaction and Retrieval* (pp. 373-377).

search can discover whether the collection offers sufficient content.²⁰ In terms of content, the Media Suite focuses on audiovisual collections, including those of the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision and the EYE Film Institute, as well as the KB newspaper collection (also in Delpher).²¹ Users have been consulted during development, leading to a balance between user-friendliness and flexibility, but also the identification of needs related to distant reading (e.g. word clouds of episodes, topic detection or automatic summaries). An extensive user evaluation is planned but has not (yet) been published.²²

Other systems that can serve as inspiration are so-called **qualitative data analysis software**.²³ Examples include NVivo, ATLAS.ti and MAXQDA. These offer broadly the same functionalities whereby texts can be annotated. Visualisations can be made of annotations and collections can be (statistically) compared. Finally, **Voyant Tools** is an interesting platform. This platform offers many options for distant reading of text collections, including word frequencies (across the whole corpus, across different breakdowns), and various analyses of words occurring together (e.g. collocations, correlations, topic models, etc.).²⁴ There seems to be no comprehensive user evaluation. Moreover, neither the above-mentioned software nor Voyant Tools are suitable for the size of the KB collections.

In summary, two things stand out from the experiences with related systems revealed in the desk research and exploratory interviews. First, developing research software for generic applications is experienced as **very complex**. Development is alternatively often linked to specific researchers who serve as case studies of what practices need to be facilitated. A disadvantage of this approach is that it offers no guarantees for application outside those case studies. Second, developers indicate that combining multiple datasets in a single search environment and offering enrichments or enrichment options are **very labour-intensive and/or computationally intensive**. If the text suite has to be flexible enough for a very diverse audience (from scholars to the interested public) and with very diverse content (KB's as well as external collections), then the existing examples offer very limited guidance. Some interviewees therefore indicated that an API might be the best solution, as it offers the greatest possible flexibility for a researcher. However, a single API may not support certain types of research, and many researchers (as well as students, journalists and the interested public) are not technically savvy enough to use APIs.²⁵

2.3 A generic description of the research process

To enable advanced digital research, it is important to get a full picture of the broader research process. User requirements for an advanced research system in text collections

²⁰ Whitelaw, M. (2015). Generous interfaces for digital cultural collections.

²¹ Datasets [mediasuitedata.clariah.nl]

²² Ordelman, R., et al. (2019, May). Media Suite: Unlocking Audiovisual Archives for Mixed Media Scholarly Research. In *Selected papers from the CLARIN Annual Conference 2018, Pisa, 8-10 October 2018* (No. 159, pp. 133-143). Linköping University Electronic Press.

²³ Top Qualitative Data Analysis Software. [predictiveanalyticstoday.com]

²⁴ List of tools. [voyant-tools.org]

²⁵ Edmond, J., & Garnett, V. (2015). APIs and Researchers: The Emperor's New Clothes? *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 10(1), 287-297. [[doi:10.2218/ijdc.v10i1.369](https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v10i1.369)]

strongly depend on subsequent research steps.²⁶ Consequently, the need for a single research step can differ considerably between users.

In recent years, several researchers have therefore attempted to conceptualise the research process in distinct steps so that intervention is possible. A tool can be used to intervene in a single step or several steps can be supported in conjunction via an infrastructure. Unsworth²⁷ describes such research steps as **scholarly primitives**; basic steps that are crucial for almost all researchers. In his first attempt, Unsworth identifies seven such scholarly primitives: discovery, annotation, comparison, referencing, sampling, illustration and display.

Research by Anderson, Blanke and Dunn²⁸ and by Blanke & Hedges²⁹ for the EHRI project (European Holocaust Research Infrastructure),³⁰ formed a grouping of scholarly primitives to support them in conjunction with a research infrastructure. The first grouping is 'discovery' where researchers seek sources from heterogeneous and dispersed collections. The second grouping is 'comparison' where researchers compare identified sources to determine whether they are relevant for the same research objective. Thus, they place activities such as annotating and referencing under this grouping. The third grouping is 'collecting' where sources from various collections are integrated in a new virtual collection. This includes sampling as a selection method. Finally, they mention the grouping 'distributing', where the virtual collection is shared with others. This involves illustrating and reproducing as distribution activities. It is worth noting that the research principle is still **mainly finding and reading sources**, without explicit focus on more computational research methods.

Research by Hoekstra & Koolen³¹ puts more emphasis on computational research methods in a description of **data-driven historical research**. They distinguish five different research phases that follow each other iteratively: selection, modelling, normalisation, linking and classification. In this, 'modelling' is a fairly generic step which can include all kinds of computational analyses where the source data is placed in a model. Examples are topic models, sentiment analyses, statistical descriptions, etc. 'Normalisation' refers to the subsequent step when sources are brought together on an equal level for integrated analysis, as in the scholarly primitive 'comparison'. 'Linking' is a step comparable to the previously mentioned referencing, where two (or more) sources are linked to each other. Finally, 'classification' is the organisation of sources under a shared denominator, comparable to the research step 'collecting' in the previous paragraph.

²⁶ Kemman, M., & Kleppe, M. (2015). User Required? On the Value of User Research in the Digital Humanities. In J. Odijk (Ed.), *Selected Papers from the CLARIN 2014 Conference, October 24-25, 2014, Soesterberg, The Netherlands* (pp. 63–74). Linköping University Electronic Press.

²⁷ Unsworth, J. (2000). Scholarly Primitives: What methods do humanities researchers have in common, and how might our tools reflect this? *Symposium on Humanities Computing: Formal Methods, Experimental Practice*.

²⁸ Anderson, S., Blanke, T., & Dunn, S. (2010). Methodological commons: Arts and humanities e-Science fundamentals. *Philosophical Transactions. Series A, Mathematical, Physical, and Engineering Sciences*, 368, 3779–3796. [doi:10.1098/rsta.2010.0156]

²⁹ Blanke, T., & Hedges, M. (2013). Scholarly primitives: Building institutional infrastructure for humanities e-Science. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 29(2), 654–661. [doi:10.1016/j.future.2011.06.006]

³⁰ European Holocaust Research Infrastructure [ehri-project.eu]

³¹ Hoekstra, R., & Koolen, M. (2018). Data scopes for digital history research. *Historical Methods: A Journal of Quantitative and Interdisciplinary History*, 1–16. [doi:10.1080/01615440.2018.1484676]

A final study relevant to this exploration is Shrikumar's PhD research.³² The exploration for the qualitative text analysis tool Wordseer³³ describes **five concrete problems** for which humanities scholars need support from a tool. As such, these five activities can also be seen as scholarly primitives for text analysis: getting an overview of the collection, visualising texts, navigating the collection, exploring the collection and collecting sources.

2.3.1 A schema of the research process with textual collections

To prepare for the interviews and to classify user requirements, we summarised the above literature in a schematic and generic representation of the research process with textual collections. Several steps have been merged (e.g. referencing and linking). In addition, there is a stronger distinction between collecting sources and analysing these sources. In the literature mentioned above, analysis is often described as a step before selecting sources. However, in this schema we position analysis as a step *after* selection in order to ask more specifically in the interviews and survey to what extent a text suite should support analysis toward research results. However, the arrow between 'selecting' and 'analysing' is depicted as a circular process to clarify that analysis can also inform the selection of sources. In addition, we refined the schema based on our interviews. It does not constitute a direct translation of the above literature.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the research process with textual collections

There are three activities in the first research **discovery** phase. First, getting an overview, so a researcher knows which sources are available within the text suite. Second, exploration, when a researcher rummages through collections in search of relevant sources. Third, search, when a researcher finds sources on the basis of search queries.

The second research phase **selection** also involves three activities. First, collecting, whereby the researcher keeps track of the relevant sources they have found. Second, sampling, where if there are too many sources, a researcher makes a well-founded selection (sample). Finally, classification, where the selection is classified and organised as a coherent whole.

The third research phase **analysis** again involves three activities. First, annotation, where a researcher adds notes to sources. Second, linking, when various sources are all linked. Third, the generic step of modelling, which can include various computational methods (such as topic models, sentiment analysis, visualisations, etc.). As described earlier, the activities in this phase follow on from the 'selection' phase, since a researcher first has to select sources

³² Shrikumar, A. (2013). *Designing an Exploratory Text Analysis Tool for Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, PhD thesis, University of California, Berkeley, pp. 48-49.

³³ [wordseer.berkeley.edu]

before they can analyse them. However, a researcher may also analyse a sample to get a classification or an overview of previous findings in order to search further.

Finally, the fourth research phase **dissemination** lists two activities. The assumption here is that the source selection or analysis results are shared with others. First, this enables collaboration, where users can jointly maintain and annotate a virtual collection. Second, one can think of sharing in publications, where an article can refer to the analysed sources.

3 Positioning a text suite

This chapter describes the information obtained from the interviews with potential users of a text suite. Group interviews were held with representatives of historical research, amateur research, literary studies, digital humanities, journalism, users of Dataservices, CLARIAH and heritage parties (see Appendix 1). During these interviews the interviewees were asked to express their expectations, wants and needs regarding a text suite's functional options (section 3.1), what types of text collections should be accessible on the platform (section 3.2) and which other heritage parties should be involved in order to explore the synergy potential for a joint text suite (section 3.3).

3.1 Users and their needs

The various user groups were asked which functionalities would be most relevant to their research activities in a KB text suite. This question was posed on the basis of the previously discussed research process schema divided into the four phases: discovery, selection, analysis and dissemination (see section 2.3.1). Several basic functions within text research are linked to these phases. In the following section, we discuss what user groups want with regard to these functions.

3.1.1 Discovery phase

Creating an overview

For the discovery phase, interviewees indicated that it is valuable to start with a **(visual) overview of the sources available** in the KB collections. Interviewees noted that it is not only important to indicate what sources are available, but also to give insight into what and why sources are *not* present in the text collection. Transparency regarding the absence of certain sources, for example because the source has not yet been digitised, is crucial in order to determine whether certain aspects were missed during the collection of sources.

In addition, interviewees wanting to use a text suite for educational purposes indicated that it is important for a text suite to be **transparent** about the processing steps conducted at the back-end of the interface to prepare the data. Without this transparency, it is difficult to guarantee the validity and reliability of research in a text suite. Moreover, they argued this provides added value for educational purposes in teaching students how to conduct sound research.

Visualising search results

The next important step in the explorative part of textual research is to visualise the search results. Interviewees indicated different needs with regard to visualisations. These differences are mainly due to the different ways of doing research: for researchers who analyse a text through *close reading*, it is relevant that an individual source is fully and pleasantly accessible in a reading window, while practitioners of *distant reading* prefer to make a quick statistical printout of a certain textual characteristic across multiple sources simultaneously.

Referring to other relevant sources

When asked if they thought being able to refer to other relevant sources within a text suite was a good idea, the potential users indicated that the added value of such referral would be the **linking between different text collections**. However, they regularly pointed out that many of the problems inherent in text research come into play here. Copyright and intellectual property rights, for example, make it difficult for texts to be accessible to a wide

audience (literary scholars say this is mainly an issue with contemporary texts). There is also a desire to make both international and regional texts available; this will be discussed in more detail in section 3.2.

3.1.2 Selection and creation of a text collection

Users frequently mentioned that when conducting textual research, they want to create their own text collection or corpus. One interviewee stated that the KB's main task is to provide access to information so that the user can carry out research independently. In the eyes of these users, the **main functionality** of a text suite should be to **combine and synthesise multiple sources**. For example, literary scholars said they need to be able to combine secondary sources with primary texts in order to achieve richer analyses.

To meet user requirements for the selection and creation of text collections, a text suite should first of all have a large number of high-quality sources at its disposal. Since the KB has the Delpher and DBNL collections, these can serve as a starting point to fill a text suite with data. Section 3.3 discusses the possibility of collaborating with others who have text collections in order to provide an even better service for text suite users.

3.1.3 Analysis

User requirements for various methods of analysis vary widely. It is striking that some users prefer to **export the compiled data** themselves for further investigation with their own analysis tools. This user group needs a well-functioning API or a user-friendly function for exporting the data, and indicated they do not require support with the actual analysis of the texts. Users who work in a less technical manner and who employ close reading, have the same export requirements as users who use their own analysis tools. They usually keep annotations on their computer in Microsoft Word or qualitative text analysis software (see section 2.2.2). Close reading is less dependent on analysis tools, and these users mainly want to retrieve sources from a text suite and read them in their own preferred environment. Some discussion partners with more quantitative objectives indicated that keeping analysis tools up to date on a platform is a major challenge. This is because of the great diversity of analysis tools and continuous changes and innovations in methods.

What is striking here is that the gap between Delpher or DBNL and Dataservices, in other words between user-friendly searching or reading and advanced analysis through programming, seems difficult to bridge. Several interviewees seemed firmly divided between these extremes, with limited need for a middle ground.

However, there is also a group that sees added value in offering more advanced functionality for analysis in a text suite. Functionality such as ngrams, sentiment analysis, word frequencies, stylometry, named entity recognition, lemmatisation and topic modelling were mentioned as valuable additions. The difference in what users want is partly because researchers with great analytical skills (in a technological sense) highly value working autonomously and prefer to carry out their research entirely independently in their own environment. Researchers with less technical experience, on the other hand, appreciate **guidance** from a text suite when performing analyses. This guidance consists of making the functionalities available within a text suite, but also an explanation for the user in the form of an infographic or short film about the added value of a particular analysis and how to carry this out.

3.1.4 Dissemination

Collaboration

Several interviewees indicated that a text suite could serve as a platform for information exchange between researchers. They noted that they regularly miss annotations when analysing data, hindering them in identifying similar sources. An advantage of a **shared platform**, such as a text suite, may be that the metadata and annotations that a researcher adds to a source are also made available to other users.

However, reuse of annotations and metadata raises a number of problems. Metadata can be generated cost-effectively by users, but this does not guarantee the uniformity of the metadata. Everyone has their own way of annotating and **without an unambiguous working method**, the compilation of collections and corpora is complicated. The annotation of metadata can also be automated (e.g. the results of topic modelling), but this method does not automatically guarantee the validity and reliability of the metadata either. This raises questions about guaranteeing quality and the sustainable preservation of annotations.

Presentation

A number of interviewees indicated that in the dissemination phase of textual research they would benefit from a dashboard function in a text suite for presenting a research study's most important **charts and exemplary texts**. In the eyes of potential users, this functionality encourages sharing of information between researchers and ensures you can quickly get a concise impression of fellow researchers' results. This could have the additional benefit of strengthening the community-building around the platform, which in turn helps users to engage with a text suite.

3.1.5 Summary of findings

Based on the interviews, we argue that the various user groups agree that the functionalities in the discovery and selection research phases are highly important. It is crucial for users that a text suite enables a quick and complete overview of which sources *can* or *cannot* be consulted. Interviewees also attached great value to the selection, combination and compilation of sources. They indicate that added value lies most strongly in the accessibility of information on the platform and that, from this perspective, a text suite must focus on the quantity, quality and completeness of the available sources. The need to expand the collection is in line with Delpher and DBNL user research (see section 2.2.1). This call is underlined by one interviewee's statement that the KB is uniquely positioned compared to research projects. After all, various research projects focus on the analysis phase of textual research, while researchers mainly need improved availability of sources.

There is a greater variety in users' wishes regarding the analysis and dissemination research phases. Some of the more technically-minded researchers stated that they prefer to analyse sources with their **own software**, methods or tools. For this group, a well-functioning API to export information is vital. At the same time, less technically-minded (amateur) researchers see little added value in advanced (quantitative) analysis tools. However, there is a group with knowledge but limited proficiency in quantitative methods and a group that wants a text suite for educational purposes, indicating it is valuable to offer a number of **basic methods** for textual research in a text suite. For these groups, in addition to offering these functionalities, it is especially important that tools are offered in combination with instructions and/or tutorials.

3.2 Text collections

This section deals with the needs and insights that the interviewees expressed regarding the availability and properties of text collections that could be offered in a text suite. The various user groups' needs are also diverse when it comes to text collections, so we will zoom in on a number of topics to analyse how the user groups differ.

3.2.1 Metadata

A significant matter that frequently came up during the interviews was the importance of metadata in text collections. Metadata enables a researcher to combine texts and search rapidly for relevant sources. Interviewees stated that this is also a major challenge because providers of diverse text collections maintain **different metadata** that is difficult to harmonise. A public platform such as a text suite could, according to some interviewees, offer opportunities to expand the available metadata via crowdsourcing, for example.

The difficulty is that different users also need different types of metadata. For example, several humanities scholars said that details on specific editions of a source (e.g. first edition, reissue) are very important for their research. When processing metadata, it is therefore necessary to think carefully in advance about the various user groups' needs. In addition, a balance must be found between increasing and enhancing the available metadata, and preserving a uniform method of annotation so that the quality of the metadata can be guaranteed. This falls **somewhat outside the scope** of the functional development of a text suite, but it is important to take into account the consequences of metadata for other functionalities such as analysis tools.

3.2.2 Importance of machine-readable texts

Interviewees expressed different opinions about the importance of machine-readable texts. Researchers who mainly conduct *close reading* do not see this as a requirement, but prefer to have more sources even if they are not (yet) machine-readable. Researchers conducting *distant reading*, however, mainly need machine-readable texts so that these can be analysed by software.

At the same time, various interviewees indicated that for many sources in e.g. Delpher, such as texts from before 1900, the OCR quality leaves much to be desired. Annotation and corrections by users were proposed as solutions. This is not only a solution for the researcher providing the annotation, but also for the next user who will work with the source. In this way, good use is made of the community on the platform. Again, this is **somewhat beyond the scope** of a text suite's functional development as it has far-reaching consequences for the sustainable management of the digital collection.

3.2.3 National or international

The focus of a KB text suite logically lies on Dutch (although also e.g. Frisian and Papiamentu) textual sources, but some interviewees also saw added value in including texts in **other languages**. Among other things, this would enable transnational research, but this request also raises a number of issues. For example, copyright law differs per country and metadata might differ between various linguistic domains, so that it is not easy to include the sources in the system unambiguously.

Besides the call for international sources, interviewees also mentioned the importance of more **regional sources** in a text suite. The inclusion of regional archives makes it possible

to carry out fine-grained research on texts from a specific region, which amateur researchers saw as a great asset.

3.2.4 Import and export

The problem of continuously updating and maintaining a large text database was emphasised by several interviewees. It is a major challenge to regularly update and supplement the data, especially if the text suite data is public and can be supplemented by users with their own annotations. At the same time, it is very important that the system shows **blind spots** in obsolete and incomplete data so that a user can assess to what extent the data needs to be supplemented.

One solution suggested by interviewees is to enable users to **import external sources** into a KB text suite. The reverse is also possible, i.e. allow users to export sources from a text suite. The preference here depends on whether a text suite offers analysis facilities. If this is the case, it will be necessary to analyse external sources within a text suite so that a researcher can work within a single environment.

3.2.5 Summary of findings

User requirements regarding the specifications and properties of text collections within a text suite vary widely. At the same time, the various groups agree on a number of overarching themes. For example, most interviewees agreed that textual research stands or falls with the availability of **high-quality metadata** and that researchers themselves can contribute to this. This dynamic is also reflected in the discussion about OCR.

It is also apparent that the **great diversity** of researchers translates into a great diversity of required text collections, varying from more international to more regional. Both are thereby dependent on an unambiguous formatting of the data to be able to conduct good research.

3.3 Collaborating with heritage organisations

Finally, the third research track in this exploration is the question whether and to what extent collaboration with other heritage organisations is possible and desirable. To answer this question, interviewees were asked their views on potential collaborations. The results are discussed below.

3.3.1 Collaboration from the start

Several interviewees emphasised that if the KB wishes to collaborate, it should do so from the start of development. In their opinion, the added value of cooperation lies in the fact that it **increases access to data sources**, but incorporating different sources into one system should be considered carefully. Therefore, an assessment of potential risks in loading and linking data sources should be made at the start of the project.

However, some interviewees feared a **sluggish decision-making process** if too many parties are involved during development. They therefore argued that it is better to take the KB collection as the starting point, and at a later stage examine how the other institutions' sources can be integrated in the platform.

3.3.2 Possible partnerships

During the interviews, several parties were identified who could be interesting partners for developing a text suite. One category is institutions with **interesting collections** for users

of the platform. The Nationaal Archief³⁴ (Dutch National Archives) was mentioned by several interviewees as a cooperation partner with an interesting collection. The question is how to offer the Nationaal Archief data to a text suite user. After all, it is an expensive undertaking to collect all the data in one central location. Some interviewees therefore preferred a **distributed model** where the data is available from various locations (i.e. institutions), and that data can then be analysed in a central text suite.

In addition to supplying data sources, **(technological) expertise** is also a possible incentive for collaboration. Parties within CLARIAH³⁵ have similar objectives to the KB and it could be useful to learn from other projects that encounter similar problems during their development. However, it was noted that CLARIAH is specifically aimed at a national scientific infrastructure, whereas the KB targets the broader section of the Dutch public (including scholars and scientists). Other parties were mentioned that could be important for the development of text analysis tools with historical text collections, such as the Institute for Dutch Language.³⁶

It might also be valuable to consider international initiatives such as CLARIN³⁷ and DARIAH,³⁸ although the interviewees thought this kind of international collaboration might be too ambitious at the start of the project.

3.3.3 Summary of findings

The interviews revealed that entering into partnerships can be very valuable for the KB when developing a text suite, both in terms of increasing the range of data sources and acquiring relevant expertise. However, establishing partnerships is also likely to increase the complexity and it is important to think carefully about the added value of potential partners.

³⁴ [nationaalarchief.nl]

³⁵ [clariah.nl]

³⁶ [idvnt.org]

³⁷ [clarin.eu]

³⁸ [dariah.eu]

4 Functional requirements

In this chapter, we discuss the outcome of the online survey conducted with potential text suite users. Based on the findings from the interviews, a questionnaire was designed to consult various user groups on a large scale about their needs. For this questionnaire, we decided to focus on functionalities that generated insufficient agreement rather than functionalities that are unanimously endorsed, such as the importance of a good search functionality. Furthermore, since no clear picture emerged of what end users think about the text collections and heritage parties for collaboration, we decided not to include these two research tracks in the questionnaire.

The survey was aimed at determining which functionalities generate the most added value and mapping the various user groups' shared priorities. For each basic functionality, respondents were asked whether they need the functionality, if they already have existing means of using such a functionality, and whether they would use it if the functionality was offered in a KB text suite. After a few introductory questions about the respondents' backgrounds, we mapped out the various user groups' priorities.

The questionnaire was distributed to existing users of KB services and other channels. Existing users were invited via the Delpher, DBNL and KB newsletters to fill in the questionnaire. In addition, the link to the survey was shared via various social media channels to reach a broad audience.

In section 4.1, we discuss the survey respondents. In section 4.2 we report the respondents' reactions to eight different functionalities that a text suite could contain. In section 4.3 we describe what respondents think about the possibility of the KB developing a text suite.

4.1 Survey respondents

A total of 873 respondents completed (some partially) the survey. To avoid losing useful information, the results also include partially completed questionnaires. As such, the response rate differs per functionality. Open questions are difficult to analyse due to the large number of respondents. We therefore use word clouds to analyse these answers.

The number of respondents drops as we get further into the questionnaire. The captions under the graphs show the total number of respondents that filled in the answers.

4.1.1 Use of KB services

A total of 873 respondents completed this part of the survey. Respondents could select multiple answers.

We see that the largest group of respondents are Delpher users, see Figure 5, with 95% of the respondents indicating that they indeed use Delpher. This is also reflected in the timing of the survey. A large proportion of the respondents completed the survey shortly after the distribution of the Delpher newsletter (which contained an invitation to the survey).

The KB Catalogue (44%), DBNL (39%) and the physical library (32%) have roughly similar proportions of users. 42 respondents (5%) have used Dataservices.

Figure 5. Responses to the question "Which KB services have you used up till now?" Respondents could select multiple answers (n=873)

4.1.2 Respondents' backgrounds

The majority of the 873 respondents ranked themselves as amateur researchers (62%). After this, we see that a large proportion of the respondents call themselves genealogists (34%) or historians (28%), see Figure 6. 55 respondents (7%) are active in digital humanities. Respondents could select multiple answers.

For the follow-up questions, we distinguish between respondents who use KB services non-professionally (amateur researchers and genealogists) and respondents who use KB services professionally (the other professions). If a respondent uses KB services both professionally and non-professionally, we classified them as professional.

Figure 6. Responses to the question "In which categories do you rank yourself when you use KB services?" Respondents could choose multiple answers (n=873)

4.2.1 Creating an overview

Of 821 respondents, 39% indicated to have a need for a visual overview of the digital sources available in the KB collections. Of these 39%, only 13% indicated they can already do so. The majority of respondents indicated that they would make use of this functionality if it was included in a text suite, see Figure 9.

Distinguishing between amateurs and professionals showed a significant difference in the current demand for a visual overview. Table 2 presents the differences. It shows that professional researchers have a greater need for a visual overview of available sources than amateur researchers.

Figure 9. Results of the questions on creating an overview of available resources

Table 2. Differences between amateur and professional researchers with regard to their need for an overview of available sources

Need for overview	Yes	No	Do not know
Amateur	36%	32%	32%
Professional	46%	25%	29%

4.2.2 Visualising search results

783 respondents answered the questions on visualisation of search results. Of these respondents, 46% had a need for such visualisations. A small number of respondents (10%) indicated that they could already do this, see Figure 11.

For this functionality too, we see significant differences between the various purposes. Respondents with quantitative purposes more often indicate a need for such visualisations, are already able to create them and would use them if offered in a text suite, see Table 4.

Figure 11. Results of the questions on visualisation of search results

Table 4. Differences between purposes for the questions on visualisation of search results

Visualising search results	Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Qualitative	50%	30%	20%
	Quantitative	69%	18%	13%
	Other	27%	52%	21%
	Pleasure	44%	31%	25%
Able	Qualitative	7%	74%	18%
	Quantitative	28%	54%	17%
	Other	12%	63%	25%
	Pleasure	8%	64%	28%
Use	Qualitative	59%	9%	33%
	Quantitative	78%	5%	16%
	Other	40%	22%	37%
	Pleasure	56%	16%	28%

4.2.4 Compiling collections

745 respondents answered the questions on compiling collections of the sources of interest they have found. There is a great demand for compiling collections: over 72% express this. On the other hand, only 28% of the respondents are currently able to do this. If compiling collections was offered in a text suite, the majority (70%) of respondents would use it, see Figure 15.

We observed significant differences in users' purposes regarding the need for compiling collections in a text suite. Groups with quantitative and qualitative research purposes have a greater need for compiling collections in a text suite, see Table 6.

Figure 15. Results of the questions regarding compiling collections

Table 6. Differences between purposes for the need to compile collections in a text suite

Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Qualitative	76%	5%	19%
Quantitative	73%	11%	16%
Other	61%	12%	26%
Pleasure	67%	11%	21%

Figure 16. Word cloud of answers (in Dutch) how users currently compile collections (n=135)

If respondents indicated they are already able to compile collections, we asked them how they currently do this. Figure 16 shows the word cloud with their answers. Respondents indicated that they mainly save texts ("bewaren"), images and/or screenshots on their own computer.

4.2.5 Qualitative analysis

720 respondents answered questions regarding qualitative analyses. This mainly concerns reading and making digital annotations on sources. Of these 720 respondents, just under half (44%) indicated that they have a need for support with qualitative analyses, see Figure 17. The proportion of respondents already able to make digital annotations is small at just 20%. If qualitative analysis functionalities were included in a text suite, less than half the respondents (44%) would use this, a substantially smaller share compared to previous functionalities. We found that professional users are significantly more likely to indicate they have a need for and can already do this analysis, see Table 7.

Qualitative analysis

Figure 17. Results of the questions regarding qualitative analysis (N= 720)

Table 7. Differences between professions with regard to qualitative analysis

Qualitative analysis	Profession	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Amateur	39%	45%	15%
	Professional	51%	37%	12%
Able	Amateur	14%	68%	18%
	Professional	27%	58%	15%

We furthermore observed significant differences in terms of purposes relating to qualitative analysis. Respondents with quantitative and qualitative research purposes have a greater need for support with qualitative analysis and are also more likely to use it if it is offered in a text suite, see Table 8.

Table 8. Differences between purposes with regard to qualitative analysis

Qualitative analysis	Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Qualitative	54%	33%	12%
	Quantitative	49%	42%	9%
	Other	29%	59%	13%
	Pleasure	36%	46%	17%
Able	Qualitative	25%	63%	12%
	Quantitative	30%	58%	12%
	Other	15%	57%	28%
	Pleasure	11%	68%	21%
Use	Qualitative	52%	20%	28%
	Quantitative	47%	25%	27%
	Other	29%	37%	34%
	Pleasure	39%	26%	36%

Table 9. Differences between professions regarding quantitative analysis.

Quantitative analysis	Profession	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Amateur	12%	57%	32%
	Professional	20%	51%	30%
Able	Amateur	5%	49%	46%
	Professional	9%	61%	30%
Use	Amateur	16%	39%	45%
	Professional	26%	31%	43%

Breaking down these responses into professional and amateur groups shows significant differences, see Table 9. Professional users notably more often demand support for quantitative analysis than amateur users and would also use this more often if it was offered in a text suite.

As with the support for qualitative analyses above, we also observed significant differences between the various purposes. The group of respondents with quantitative research purposes more often indicated that they have a need for this analysis, are already able to do this and would use it if it was in a text suite, see Table 10. This is not entirely unexpected, although it creates a more nuanced picture compared to the interviews where some quantitative researchers said they would rather use their own tools (see section 3.1.3).

Table 10. Differences between purposes for questions on quantitative analyses

Quantitative analysis	Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Qualitative	14%	53%	34%
	Quantitative	47%	36%	16%
	Other	6%	67%	27%
	Pleasure	13%	54%	33%
Able	Qualitative	7%	57%	37%
	Quantitative	17%	56%	28%
	Other	3%	39%	58%
	Pleasure	4%	55%	40%
Use	Qualitative	21%	29%	50%
	Quantitative	45%	22%	33%
	Other	9%	54%	37%
	Pleasure	18%	40%	42%

Table 12. Differences between purposes regarding quantitative analyses

Methods	Purpose	Yes	No
NER	Qualitative	15%	85%
	Quantitative	25%	75%
	Other	7%	93%
	Pleasure	13%	87%
Topic modelling	Qualitative	11%	89%
	Quantitative	38%	62%
	Other	5%	95%
	Pleasure	9%	91%
Frequency analysis	Qualitative	9%	91%
	Quantitative	35%	65%
	Other	3%	97%
	Pleasure	5%	95%
Sentiment analysis	Qualitative	7%	93%
	Quantitative	24%	76%
	Other	2%	98%
	Pleasure	4%	96%
Clustering	Qualitative	11%	89%
	Quantitative	27%	73%
	Other	5%	95%
	Pleasure	10%	90%

Table 13. Differences between professions regarding quantitative analyses

Methods	Profession	Yes	No
NER	Amateur	89%	11%
	Professional	82%	18%
Topic modelling	Amateur	93%	7%
	Professional	83%	17%
Frequency analysis	Amateur	95%	5%
	Professional	86%	14%
Sentiment analysis	Amateur	97%	3%
	Professional	88%	12%
Clustering	Amateur	91%	9%
	Professional	85%	15%

4.2.7 Reuse of data

715 respondents answered questions regarding reuse of data, whereby metadata and annotations from other researchers can be used. We see that only a small number of respondents have a need to reuse data (20%), see Figure 21. An even smaller number indicate that they already do so (6%). We did not ask whether people would reuse data if this was offered in a text suite.

Figure 21. Results of the questions regarding reuse of data (N= 715)

Table 14. Differences between purposes regarding need for reusing data

Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Qualitative	25%	34%	42%
Quantitative	30%	37%	33%
Other	14%	49%	37%
Pleasure	15%	36%	49%

If we distinguish the various purposes we see a significant difference in the need for reusing data. The respondents with quantitative and qualitative research purposes indicate a greater need for reusing data compared to other users, see Table 14.

We asked respondents how they currently reused data. Their answers (in Dutch) were visualised in a word cloud, see Figure 22. It is striking that archives ("archieven") and catalogues ("catalogus") are important sources of data, yet respondents also regularly seek contact with other researchers through associations ("lidmaatschap") or personal contact ("aanschrijven"). Nederlab also stands out in this word cloud.

Figure 22. Word cloud of responses to how data is currently reused (n=17)

4.2.8 Presenting of results

Finally, we asked about the options for presenting research results (the collection of documents and possibly analysis results), for example with a dashboard. 704 respondents answered questions about this. Only 16% indicated that they have a need to present results, see Figure 23. An even smaller proportion of respondents are already able to do this (6%). Remarkably, a larger share of respondents indicated that they would use this feature if it was available in a text suite (21%).

Figure 23. Responses regarding questions on presenting of results

Table 15. Differences between purposes regarding presenting of results

Presentation of results	Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know
Need	Qualitative	20%	55%	25%
	Quantitative	28%	48%	24%
	Other	9%	65%	26%
	Pleasure	12%	66%	22%
Use	Qualitative	27%	34%	40%
	Quantitative	30%	28%	43%
	Other	10%	50%	39%
	Pleasure	17%	49%	34%

Figure 24. Word cloud of responses (in Dutch) how users currently present their results (n=14).

If we break down the various purposes, we find significant differences in current demand and potential use of presentation functionalities in a text suite, see Table 15. Respondents with qualitative and quantitative research purposes are more likely to indicate a need for presentation functionality and are also more likely to use it in a text suite.

We asked respondents how they currently present results. Their answers are shown in Figure 24 as a word cloud (in Dutch). Excel, Powerpoint and the respondents' own websites are most often mentioned.

4.3 Development of a text suite by the KB

We asked respondents whether they would like the KB to develop a text suite. We see that the majority of respondents had no opinion on this. Of the respondents with an opinion, the majority are positive (32% yes compared to 10% no), see Figure 25.

If we distinguish between the various purposes, we find significant differences. The group of respondents with quantitative research purposes is more positive about the KB developing a text suite than the other groups, see Table 16.

We also found a significant difference between amateur and professional users, with professional users more positive about the KB developing a text suite, see Table 17.

Figure 25. Responses to: "Do you want the KB to create a text suite that offers the functionality you need?" (N= 700).

Table 16. Differences between purposes regarding the desirability of the KB developing a text suite

Purpose	Yes	No	Do not know / No opinion
Qualitative	38%	6%	56%
Quantitative	48%	7%	44%
Other	24%	17%	60%
Pleasure	24%	14%	62%

Table 17. Differences between professions wanting the KB to develop a text suite

Profession	Yes	No	Do not know / No opinion
Amateur	27%	11%	62%
Professional	38%	10%	53%

We asked the 222 respondents who were positive about the KB developing a text suite in what way such a text suite could be integrated in in the KB's range of services. The respondents could choose between integration in existing services, a separate service or a programming environment. The majority prefer integration within existing services such as Delpher or DBNL, see Figure 26.

Remarkably, we found no significant differences between the respondents with quantitative research purposes and other respondents with regard to design. This is contrary to our expectation that respondents with quantitative research purposes would prefer a programming environment (see also the use of python in Figure 20).

Figure 26. Responses to: "What form of text suite would best match your needs as a user?" (n=222)

5 Conclusions and recommendations

In this chapter we describe the study's main findings. Based on our desk research, interviews and online survey, we present in section 5.1 our conclusions regarding the added value of a text suite and regarding the research on user requirements, text collections and heritage parties for collaboration. Finally, in section 5.2 we provide recommendations for developing a text suite.

5.1 Conclusions

5.1.1 Users and their wishes

The focus of this research is to arrive at a demand-driven description of a text suite. With regard to user requirements, we conclude:

1. DBNL and Delpher user research gives limited indications of the added value of a text suite. More advanced options currently available are only used to a limited extent. Advanced research methods are also not mentioned, or only to a limited extent, as options for improving these services. Delpher's personas moreover provide little guidance for developing a text suite.
2. Alternative research systems also provide limited indications of the added value of a text suite. In many cases there has been limited user research and these systems are mainly aimed at humanities scholars. However, some aspects can serve as inspiration, including the principle of generous interfaces whereby a visual overview of available sources can stimulate users.
3. The interviews highlight that it seems difficult to bridge the gap between Delpher or DBNL and Dataservices, in other words between user-friendly searching or reading and advanced analysis through programming. Interviewees are divided between these extremes, with limited need for a middle ground.
4. Based on the literature, we distinguish four research phases: discovery, selection, analysis and dissemination.
5. There is a clear need for advanced capabilities in the discovery phase. Interviewees and online survey respondents either expressed an explicit demand for visualisations of availability and search results, or indicated that they will use this if it is available.
6. There is also a clear need for advanced capabilities in the selection phase. Interviewees and survey respondents indicated a strong need for compiling collections of interesting sources.
7. There is no clear need for advanced capabilities in the analysis phase. Although this was the starting point for the exploration, interviewees and survey respondents indicated that they have less need for it and would also use it less if it was offered. We find that:
 - a. Because of the great heterogeneity of source material from the KB and elsewhere, researchers prefer to bring everything together on their own computer for analysis. The alternative is that a text suite makes it possible to import sources, which raises questions about the sustainable preservation of combined collections.
 - b. Because of the rapid development of especially quantitative analysis tools, interviewees see a risk that the KB will offer tools that quickly become outdated, especially if they are used too little to warrant much effort in continuous development.
 - c. If analysis functionality is offered in existing platforms (e.g. the n-gram viewer in DBNL or frequency analysis in Nederlab), this does not appear to lead to

recognition and broad application for new research questions. We therefore conclude that the latent need for such functionalities seems limited.

- d. Interviewees do however see added value in supporting the further process of analysing sources. This can be done by offering a number of basic functions. It could also involve providing documentation or an explanation of how to analyse (large) text collections. A text suite can also play an educational role here.
8. There is no clear need for advanced options in the dissemination phase. Survey respondents indicate less need for this. Interviewees express a great need to be able to collaborate as a community on text collections, sharing annotations and improving metadata and OCR. However, this raises questions regarding sustainable storage and the quality and uniformity of (meta)data.
9. A text suite mainly seems to serve research (especially professional) needs. Amateur researchers and respondents who use Delpher and/or DBNL for pleasure have less need for a new service and mainly see room for improvement in existing services.

5.1.2 Text collections

With regard to incorporating different text collections, we conclude:

1. DBNL and Delpher user surveys consistently show that expanding collections is the most important point for improvement.
2. We observe that there is a wide variety of text collections that people need, depending on their individual research questions. This varies from regional sources to international data collections, and from data to not yet machine-readable sources. It is not feasible to make a selection of collections that every user can work with entirely.
3. In this respect, interviewees state that combining collections is a major challenge, as providers of diverse text collections keep different metadata that is difficult to harmonise. Other research systems show that combining multiple collections with enrichments is very labour-intensive and computationally demanding.
4. Various users emphasise the added value of crowdsourcing for supplementing and improving metadata and OCR. We note, however, that this falls outside the scope of the functional development of a text suite as it has far-reaching consequences for the sustainable management of digital collections.
5. The importance of incorporating external collections depends partly on whether a text suite offers analysis facilities. If it does, this will consequently lead to a demand for analysing external sources within a text suite so that a researcher can work within a single environment. If researchers export data from a text suite for analysis on their own computer, there is a less pronounced need for full integration of multiple text collections.

5.1.3 Heritage organisations for collaboration

With regard to collaboration with other heritage parties, we conclude:

1. Interviewees consider collaboration important primarily for increasing the availability of collections and involving necessary (technological) expertise.
2. However, they also indicate that too many partners will make development too sluggish, as various interests have to be negotiated. Especially when combining several text collections, there is a risk that too much time will be lost in harmonising metadata.
3. We assess that the KB, with Delpher and DBNL as well as other internal collections, has sufficient material to form a starting point for a text suite. The most important next step is looking at the Nationaal Archief (National Archives) collections.

5.2 Recommendations

We conclude that there are sufficient opportunities to develop a text suite. Our recommendations for this development are:

1. **Position a text suite as a corpus selection tool and support the discovery and selection research phases.** A text suite hereby functions as a user-friendly front end to Dataservices with more advanced features that do not fit within Delpher and DBNL. Users can then make their own selection of sources and export them (possibly after approval by a KB employee).
2. **Develop advanced search and selection functionalities.** We recommend including the following functionalities:
 - a. search bar
 - b. filtering based on metadata fields
 - c. filtering search results based on metadata fields
 - d. visualisations of available sources
 - e. visualisations of search results
 - f. options for compiling your own collections, e.g. by adding individual sources or large quantities of search results
 - g. searching within your own collections
 - h. filtering within your own collections based on metadata fields
 - i. visualisations of your own collections
 - j. options to export sources and/or collections.
3. **Recalibrate the aims regarding analysis support.** We see insufficient commonly shared needs for developing an advanced analysis tool. Moreover, in terms of analysis methodology, we see insufficient need to bridge the gap between Delpher and DBNL on the one hand and Dataservices on the other. We also see a risk of analysis tools becoming outdated and/or being underused for continuous development, which could harm the KB's image. We find that educational support is needed for the analysis phase. This could include tutorials and documentation on how to use a selection of sources from a text suite sources with other software tools.
4. **Start with a broad base of KB collections and explore collaboration with the Nationaal Archief (Dutch National Archives).** There is too much diversity in the collections with different metadata and quality standards to enable a text suite to start making a large number of text collections from different providers equally searchable. Moreover, the KB manages a very rich diversity of collections which provide a sufficient starting point for a text suite. Nationaal Archief could be an added value partner from the start because then the archival material perspective (as opposed to library collections) could be incorporated in the development. Moreover, Nationaal Archief manages richly diverse collections too and in recent years has been making great strides in having collections available for digital infrastructures.

Appendix 1. Interviewees

Name	Background	User group
Bas Doppen	CLARIAH	
Dirk de Geest	KU Leuven	Literary scholar
Ed Ploeg	Amateur researcher	Amateur researcher
Els Stronks	Utrecht University	Literary scholar
Elsbeth Kwant	KB (Strategic advisor)	
Ewoud Sanders	NRC	Journalist
Hennie Brugman	KNAW / CLARIAH	
Joris van Zundert	Huygens Institute	
Karina van Dalen-Oskam	Huygens Institute	
Leon Wessels	CLARIN ERIC / Utrecht University	
Lieke van Deinsen	KU Leuven	Literary scholar
Liesbeth Keijzer	Nationaal Archief	Heritage organisation
Lucas van der Deijl	University of Amsterdam	Literary scholar
Lucinda Jones	KB (Head of Collections) / Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE)	
Maaïke Napolitano	KB (coordinator Delpher)	
Marten Düring	Leiden University	
Martijn Kleppe	KB (Head of Research)	
Maud Ehrmann	École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)	
Melvin Wevers	University of Amsterdam	Digital Humanities
Michiel Cock	VU University Library	Heritage organisation
Milan van Lange	Utrecht University / NIOD	Digital Humanities
Norah Karrouche	Erasmus University Rotterdam / VU University Amsterdam	Historian
Puck Wildschut	Utrecht University Library	Heritage organisation
Roeland Ordelman	NISV	
Ronald van der Heijden	Independent historian	Historian
Steven Claeysens	KB (Conservator digital collections)	
Susan Aasman	University of Groningen	Digital Humanities
Wim de Natris	Independent historian	Historian
Wim Drost	Amateur researcher	Amateur research

Contact:

Dialogic innovatie & interactie
Hooghiemstraplein 33-36
3514 AX Utrecht
Tel. +31 (0)30 215 05 80
www.dialogic.nl

